

Microwave-assisted alkaline fusion followed by water-leaching for the selective extraction of the refractory metals tungsten, niobium and tantalum from low-grade ores and tailings

Jeroen Spooren¹ *, Wendy Wouters¹, Bart Michiels¹, Elena M. Seftel¹, Steven-Friso Koelewijn¹

¹ Materials and Chemistry, Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO n.v.), Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium

* Corresponding author: jeroen.spooren@vito.be

Keywords: alkaline fusion; columbite-tantalite; hydrometallurgy; microwave pre-treatment; refractory metals; scheelite

ABSTRACT

The refractory metals tungsten, tantalum and niobium are considered critical raw materials in Europe. Diversifying the supply of such materials, for instance by recovering refractory metals from local low-grade ore materials could reduce their supply risks. However, the extraction processes require to be efficient with a low energy and material consumption and a minimal environmental impact. In this work, microwave (MW) assisted alkaline fusion was explored to extract tungsten from scheelite containing ore materials with different grades (high to very low) and tantalum and niobium from a columbite-tantalite $[(\text{Fe},\text{Mn})(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_6]$ concentrate. During

the fusion process scheelite was converted into soluble alkali tungstate salts [Na_2WO_4 , K_2WO_4 and/or $\text{K}_3\text{Na}(\text{WO}_4)_2$] and the reaction temperature could be lowered to 150-200 °C by fusion with a low-melting eutectic alkali salt system of an 1:1 (m/m) NaOH:KOH mixture. The application of MW-assisted heating allowed for fast and volumetric heating, thereby lowering reaction times to 10 min – 30 min. After fusion, tungsten was extracted by a simple water leaching step leading to extraction efficiencies ranging from 77% to 97%. Noteworthy, also P, S and As, which all form soluble oxyanions were extracted from the studied materials. Extraction of niobium and tantalum was also achieved through MW-assisted alkaline fusion as an alternative to acidic fluorine-based hydrometallurgical processes. MW-assisted heating allowed for a fast conversion of the $(\text{Fe},\text{Mn})(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_6$ into alkali tantalate and niobate salts. Under optimal conditions, MW-assisted fusion with KOH (salt:sample = 3:1 (m/m)) at 400 °C for 10 min leached ca. 74%-88% of tantalum and 77%-86% of niobium into water (L/S = 10) at 40 °C for 120 min, while the main matrix elements Mn and Fe displayed limited dissolution (<4%). Due to the low solubility of sodium tantalate and niobate salts in water, MW-assisted alkaline fusion in an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture followed by water leaching was not efficient.

► Introduction

Tungsten (W), tantalum (Ta) and niobium (Nb) are transition metals with unique features and properties that make them indispensable for many key industrial sectors. Tungsten has the highest melting point (3422 °C) of all metals and its alloys are used in many high temperature applications. One of the most important tungsten products is tungsten carbide, which is an extremely hard alloy of high importance for the petroleum sector, mining industries and cutting tools. Likewise, tantalum has a very high melting point (3020 °C) and is used for cutting tools and military projectiles, but also as a key material in high-performance capacitors due to its unique properties (Cardonne et al., 1995). Over 90% of niobium is used in steels and as a grain refiner, where very small additions (200 - 1000 g t⁻¹), significantly increase both steel strength and toughness (Baker et al., 2002). Moreover, thanks to its superconducting properties, niobium is a key material in the production of superconducting magnets (Finnemore et al., 1966). These three metals are listed by the European Commission as critical raw materials (CRMs), which identifies materials that are economically and strategically important for the European economy but have a high-risk associated with their supply (DG GROW - European Commission, 2023). Additionally, tungsten has also been defined by the same Commission as a strategic raw material, playing a pivotal role to reach the European Union's strategic goals (DG GROW - European Commission, 2023). Considering this background, recycling of these valuable metals from residue streams, such as mine tailings, and recovering them from alternative low-grade resources is vital for economic development. Furthermore, upon extracting metals even from low-grade materials the remaining mineral matrix materials could be purified from possible hazardous (heavy) metals and can thus help to minimize disposal costs and environmental problems in mining and mineral processing according to near-zero waste principles (Spooren et al., 2020).

Several processes are used to extract niobium and tantalum from high grade ores. The most applied process consists of leaching the ores in hydrofluoric acid, generating large amounts of wastewater. Due to the use of HF this process is considered hazardous. Acid leaching can also use H_2SO_4 (El-Hussaini and Mahdy, 2002) instead of HF (Majima et al., 1988) as leaching agent, or a mixture of these acids (El-Hussaini and Mahdy, 2002; Krismer and Hoppe, 1984). Yet, this method typically results in a low extraction efficiency of the target metals (Chen et al., 2019). Other methods consist of high temperature processes, such as alkali fusion ($800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) (Wang et al., 2009) or reducing chlorination ($900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) (Bohnet, 2003). The latter process produces large amounts of phosgene and chlorine containing waste gas. For the former process, Wang et al., 2009 (Wang et al., 2009) applied an alkali roasting using KOH and a subsequent water leaching step to extract niobium and tantalum from an ore material containing 27.05 wt% Nb_2O_5 and 25.00 wt% Ta_2O_5 . During the roasting step a KOH-to-ore mass ratio of 2:1 was used, and reaction took place at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 60 min, leading to about 95 % niobium and 94 % tantalum extraction yields. It should be noted that in the above case the melting point of KOH ($T_m = 360\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) has been exceeded, for which the applied reaction procedure is often referred to as alkaline fusion. In the case of tungsten recovery from ore materials, alkaline digestion is the preferred industrial scale route to extract the metal (Lassner, 1995). The alkaline fusion approach, applying Na_2CO_3 or NaOH, and in some cases NaNO_3 as an oxidation agent, has been also used to recovery tungsten from both primary ore materials and scrap. As the water solubilities of typical tungsten ore minerals scheelite (CaWO_4) and ferberite (FeWO_4) are very low (Foster, 1977), alkaline fusion has the aim of producing the soluble sodium tungstate (Na_2WO_4), to allow for subsequent water leaching (Choi et al., 2019; Lassner, 1995; Srinivas et al., 2000) (Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of alkaline fusion methods to recover W, Ta and Nb

Ore material	Metal recovery rate	Salt	Optimised reaction conditions			Ref.
			Ratio	T (°C)	t (min)	
Spent SCR catalyst (7.11 wt% WO ₃ , 0.98 wt% V ₂ O ₅)	>99% V and W	Na ₂ CO ₃	Molar ratio MO _x /(Na ₂ O + MO _x) (M= Ti, Si and W) = 0.5	950	20	(Choi et al., 2019)
Wolframite-scheelite concentrate (21.21 wt% WO ₃ , 5.0 wt% Sn)	±95% W	Na ₂ CO ₃ + NaNO ₃	Mass ratio Na ₂ CO ₃ :NaNO ₃ :feed = 1.5:0.5:1	550	120	(Srinivas et al., 2000)
Low-grade ore (27.05 wt% Nb ₂ O ₅ , 25.00 wt% Ta ₂ O ₅ , niobite-tantalite and cassiterite)	95% Nb, 94% Ta	KOH	Mass ratio Nb ₂ O ₅ -to-Ta ₂ O ₅ = 2.33:1; Mass ratio KOH:ore = 2:1	400	60	(Wang et al., 2009)
Tantalite from a pegmatite-spudomene ore (55.71 wt% Ta ₂ O ₅ , 5.51 wt% Nb ₂ O ₅)	97.7% Nb, 75.8% Ta	KOH	Mass ratio KOH:tantalite = 5:1	400	60	(Berhe et al., 2018)
Concentrate (1.985 wt% Nb ₂ O ₅ , 0.045 wt% Ta ₂ O ₅)	98% Nb	KOH	Mass ratio KOH:concentrate = 2:1	550	150	(Abdel Wahab et al., 2019)
Coltan ore (8.5 wt% Nb, 19 wt% Ta)	87% Nb, 80% Ta	KOH	Mass ratio KOH:ore = 3:1	550	60	(Shikika et al., 2021)
Columbite concentrate (2.67 wt% Nb ₂ O ₅ , 4.98 wt% Ta ₂ O ₅); Coltan concentrate (4.85 wt% Nb ₂ O ₅ , 4.64 wt% Ta ₂ O ₅)	92-94% Nb, 91-92% Ta (columbite) 92-94% Nb, 91-92% Ta (coltan)	KOH	Mass ratio KOH:concentrate = 1:1	250	60	(Habshuti et al., 2023)

Fusion with molten and sub-molten alkali salts seems a promising technique for the recovery of the refractory metals tantalum, niobium and tungsten from secondary raw materials. However, the process could have an increased operation cost since reactions operate at high temperature (>400 °C) and consume significant amounts of alkali (Table 1). Using microwave (MW) heating instead of conventional heating during alkali fusion can overcome some of the drawbacks. MW heating, used in extractive metallurgy, leads to rapid chemical reactions with lower reagents and energy consumption (Peng and Hwang, 2014). Furthermore, using an eutectic mixture of alkaline salts can significantly reduce the salts melting temperature (e.g., $T_m(\text{KOH}) = 360\text{ °C}$ and $T_m(\text{NaOH}) = 323\text{ °C}$, while $T_m(49\text{ mol\% KOH}:51\text{ mol\% NaOH}) = 170\text{ °C}$). Microwave energy was already applied to the extraction of various metals (Abo Atia and Spooren, 2020a, b; Abo Atia et al., 2021; Pickles, 2009a, b; Pinto and Soares, 2013; Spooren and Abo Atia, 2020; Wen et al., 2017). Sanchez-Segado et al. (2017) investigated the potential application of MW-heating for the alkaline roasting of a columbite concentrate by a careful study of the mineral changes and dielectric properties of a 1:1 columbite – sodium bicarbonate mixture over a wide temperature range from room temperature up to 1000 °C. Recently, MW-heating was indeed applied for the alkali treatment of a ferro-columbite concentrate. Herein, the columbite concentrate was mixed with potassium hydroxide in a 1:1 (m/m) ratio and subsequently placed in a microwave furnace operated at 2450 MHz for 5.6 min at 680 W, yielding a 94% niobium and 88% tantalum extraction during subsequent water leaching (Tanvar and Mishra, 2024; Tanvar et al., 2023). During the treatment the sample heated to above 900 °C. The application of MW-heating yielded a short treatment time as compared to conventional heating at 300 °C (i.e., 60 min), as well as a 12 times energy consumption reduction.

This study investigates the extraction of tungsten, niobium and tantalum from intermediate and low-grade primary and secondary ore materials via alkaline fusion using microwave heating

technology, with the aim of achieving high leaching efficiency and limiting the energy consumption of this process compared to conventional heating systems by shortening reaction times. The goal was to optimize the MW-assisted alkaline fusion step in terms of the reaction parameters roasting time and temperature, and the amount and the type of alkali salt added. In the subsequent leaching step, extraction parameters were studied (i.e., liquid-to-solid (L/S) ratio, dwelling time and temperature) with the aim of maximizing target metal dissolution.

Materials and methods

Materials

In this study a high-grade scheelite ore concentrate (DB-26), an intermediate grade ore (DB-91) and a gravity tailing (DB-52) were supplied by the Barruecopardo mine in the Salamanca area of Spain, exploited by Saloro. Furthermore, a tungsten concentrate (DB-141) was produced by the University of Liege (Belgium) from the gravity tailing material through density-based physical separation processes. Additionally, a tantalum-niobium-concentrate (DB-139) of a cassiterite ore material from the Penouta mine in the Spanish province of Ourense, exploited by Strategic Minerals, was used to explore MW-assisted alkaline fusion for the extraction of tantalum and niobium. This concentrate was obtained through high intensity magnetic separation and an electrostatic treatment at the mining site. The sample naming refers to the sample database (DB) numbering of the H2020 TARANTULA project (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/821159>) in which this research took place.

MW-assisted alkaline fusion reactions were performed in the presence of KOH powder (*Sigma-Aldrich*, for synthesis ($\geq 85\%$), CAS-No. 1310-58-3) and/or NaOH pellets (*Merck, EMSURE®*, for analysis ($\geq 98\%$), CAS-No. 1310-73-2). The NaOH pellets were ground by pestle and mortar before use. Both alkali salts were dried in an oven at 40 °C prior to use. MilliQ water was used for water leaching reactions.

Alkaline fusion and water leaching

MW-assisted fusion was performed using a PyroWave advanced microwave furnace (Milestone) equipped with a 1.2 kW magnetron and operating at a MW frequency of 2450 MHz in multimode. The maximum operating temperature of this system is 1200 °C. The microwave was equipped with a silicon carbide (SiC) plate at the top of the heating chamber. This plate was installed to ensure a uniform temperature inside the heating chamber as it heats up very fast under MW irradiation and releases the heat to the heating chamber by convection and thermal radiation. Also, materials placed in the furnace that are prone to heat through MW absorption could absorb remnant MWs which were not absorbed by the SiC plate, for which the exact temperature of the samples during reaction was unknown. Nevertheless, this latter effect is minimal.

In a first step, the tungsten- or tantalum/niobium-containing materials were mixed in a mortar with the required amount of alkaline salt (NaOH ($T_m = 323$ °C) and/or KOH ($T_m = 360$ °C)). For the experiments using combination of both NaOH and KOH, an equiponderant NaOH:KOH (i.e., 1:1 (m/m)) ($T_m \approx 198$ °C) was used for the tungsten-containing material, while an equimolar NaOH:KOH (i.e., 1:1 (mol/mol)) ($T_m \approx 175$ °C) was used for the tantalum/niobium containing material, respectively. Subsequently, the solid mixtures were placed in a crucible which was introduced in a MW furnace. Typically, each crucible was filled with 6 g of the solid mixture in case of tungsten containing samples and 12 g in case of tantalum/niobium containing samples. Up to 6 crucibles could be placed in the muffle inside the MW furnace per batch. The samples were fused in the Milestone PyroWave MW furnace and after cooling the fused materials were water leached in a conventionally heated shaking water bath. Then vacuum filtration took place and the resulting leachates and extracted solid residues were examined by ICP-OES and XRF, respectively. Additionally, XRD was used to monitor mineralogical transformations in the fused materials and leaching residues. MW-

assisted alkaline fusion experiments were performed in triplicate and subsequent water leaching was performed on two of the roasted samples (i.e., in duplicate).

The leaching efficiency $E_L(M)$, expressed in %, of an extracted element M was calculated according to

$$E_L(M) = \frac{V_L \times C_L}{m_i \times C_i} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

whereby V_L is the volume of the leachate (in L), C_L the concentration of the element in the obtained leachate (in mg/L), m_i the initial mass of the treated W- or Ta/Nb-material (in kg) and C_i the concentration of the considered element in the starting material (in mg/kg ds).

Alternatively, in some cases the leaching efficiency was calculated based on the elemental analysis of the solid leaching residue according to

$$E_L(M) = \frac{(m_i \times C_i) - (m_R \times C_R)}{m_i \times C_i} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

whereby m_R is the mass of the solid residue after leaching (in kg) and C_R the concentration of the considered element in the solid residue (in mg/kg ds).

In the below text the reported leaching efficiencies are always calculated based on Eq. (1), unless otherwise stated.

In the lixivants of the tantalum/niobium treated by NaOH:KOH fusion, a precipitate was formed that was further analysed. The precipitate was filtered off by a *SCP Science DigiFilter* system. The obtained residue was air dried and subsequently recovered from the filter. The solid was digested (3 mL HCl, 1 mL HNO₃, 2 mL HF, 2 h at 105 °C) and the obtained digestate was neutralised by 22 mL H₃BO₃ addition and then analysed by ICP-OES.

Analysis methods

The mineralogical composition of samples was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) through a *PANalytical EMPYREAN* system, operated at 40 kV and 45 mA, with a cobalt anode and equipped with a BBHD (Bragg Brentano High Definition) and a 3D detector (*PIXcel 3D*) with an active scanning length of $3.347^\circ 2\theta$. Continuous mode scans with a scanning speed of

0.06°/sec and step size of 0.013° were performed within a 2θ range of 5°-120°. Obtained diffractograms were qualitatively and quantitatively analysed with the aid of *HighScore Plus* software.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) by a FEI Quanta 200 scanning electron microscope equipped with a Bruker Xflash 4030 EDS detector were used to determine the composition, elemental distribution, and morphology of epoxy embedded powder samples.

A handheld XRF analyser *Niton XL3t GOLDD+*, equipped with an Ag anode (50 kV and 0.2 mA), was used for chemical elemental analysis of all solid samples. The XRF analyser was placed in a mobile test stand during all measurements and a measuring time of 120 s. was applied for each sample. Some solid samples were analyzed using a high-performance energy-dispersive XRF (EDXRF) spectrometer with polarized X-ray excitation geometry (*XEPOS HE, Spectro Analytical Systems, Kleve, Germany*) under He atmosphere. The instrument was equipped with a 50-W tungsten end window tube (maximum 60 kV, 2 mA) and a Silicon Drift Detector. The dried and finely ground samples were analyzed as loose powder. For analysis as loose powder, an XRF sampling cup, provided with a 4- μ m prolene foil (*Chemplex, Palm City, FL, USA*), was filled with the sample and subsequently placed in the autosampler of the EDXRF system. The quantification was performed using a pre-calibrated software package (*Spectro X-LABPro Version 5.1, Spectro Analytical Instruments, Kleve, Germany*) for (semi)-quantitative analysis of geological materials.

The metal content in the sample was also determined with inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) after acid digestion using a heating block. About 0.1 g of sample was weighed into the digestion vessel. Then, the following acids were separately added: 3 mL of HCl, 1 mL of HNO₃, and 2 mL of HBF₄. The digestion vessel was placed into the heating block (*Digiprep MS, Benelux Scientific, Belgium*) and heated during 2 hours at 105 °C.

At the end of the program, the vessels were cooled down to room temperature and filled up to 50 mL with ultrapure water. Prior to analysis the samples were filtered ($< 0.45 \mu\text{m}$) and measured with an ICP-OES (*Agilent 5100, Agilent Technologies, Belgium*). Only the elements U and Hg were measured with inductively coupled plasma sector field mass spectrometry ICP-SFMS (*Element II, ThermoFisher, Belgium*), using the same digestion solution and after dilution. Eluate samples were analyzed – after the proper dilution - directly with ICP-OES (*Agilent 5100, Agilent Technologies, Belgium*).

► **Results and discussion**

Starting material characterization

The high-grade concentrate (DB-26) (52.6 wt% W) was used as a model material to study the effect of MW-assisted alkaline fusion and the occurring reaction mechanism. The main tungsten mineral phase, namely scheelite (CaWO_4) was observed, together with traces of ferberite (FeWO_4) and fluoroapatite ($\text{Ca}_5\text{F}(\text{PO}_4)_3$) phases. Next, an intermediate grade scheelite ore (DB-91), containing 3.67 wt% W, was studied which was rich in the aluminosilicates muscovite ($\text{K}(\text{Al,Fe})_2(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2$), orthoclase ($(\text{K,Na})\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_8$) and albite ($\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$), and quartz (SiO_2). Similar mineral compositions were observed for the gravity tailing material (DB-52) with 0.1 wt% W and a concentrate (DB-141) with 1.0 wt% W obtained from the tailing material through density-based mineral unit processing. The tantalum and niobium concentrate (DB-139) contained equal high amounts of tantalum (15.9 wt%) and niobium (15.9 wt%) which are present in a columbite ($(\text{Fe,Mn})(\text{Nb,Ta})_2\text{O}_6$) mineral phase in the material. However, the material was mainly amorphous and not all diffraction peaks of the X-ray diffractogram could be assigned to a mineral phase. The elemental composition of the studied samples and their XRD diffractograms are shown in the Supplementary Information (Table S1 and Figure S1).

Alkaline microwave-assisted fusion of scheelite ores

Initial experiments were performed on the high grade scheelite ore material DB-26 to investigate the scheelite conversion reaction. The reaction parameters, such as fusion temperature and alkali salt addition, namely using NaOH versus an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture of 1:1 (m/m) were studied. XRD analyses revealed that – already at 150-200 °C – CaWO₄ (scheelite) reacts with NaOH:KOH (1:1 (m/m)) during the fusion reaction to form Na₂WO₄, K₂WO₄ and/or K₃Na(WO₄)₂, as well as portlandite (Ca(OH)₂) (Figure 1), confirming that the following cation exchange reactions took place (eq. 3-5).

Also, in the case of NaOH fused material at 150 °C, far below the melting point of NaOH ($T_m = 318$ °C), the presence of Na₂WO₄ was already observed. Noteworthy, in the NaOH fused sample at 500 °C, the presence of the Na₂WO₄·2H₂O hydrated tungstate salt was observed and the intensity of portlandite (Ca(OH)₂) peaks in the diffractogram was lower as compared to the other samples. The latter observation can be assigned to the dehydration of Ca(OH)₂ to CaO, which occurs upon heating in the temperature range 330-450 °C (Irabien et al., 1990). Whereas it could be hypothesized that the strongly hygroscopic CaO adsorbed water from the air upon cooling the sample, which could consequently hydrate the sodium tungstate salt.

Figure 1: XRD analyses of DB-26 material MW-assisted fused at different temperatures for 30 min in the presences of NaOH (top left) or NaOH:KOH = 1:1 (m/m) (top right), both with a sample:salt mass ratio of 1:1. The diffractogram of the water-leaching residues (60 °C, 2 h, L/S = 10) of the fused samples are depicted below. (S – scheelite (CaWO_4); N – Na_2WO_4 / K_2WO_4 ; n – natrite (Na_2CO_3); P – portlandite ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$); H – $\text{Na}_2\text{WO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; t – thermonatrite ($\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$); K – $\text{K}_3\text{Na}(\text{WO}_4)_2$; F – ferberite (FeWO_4); f – fluoroapatite ($\text{Ca}_5\text{F}(\text{PO}_4)_3$); Q – quartz (SiO_2); C – calcite (CaCO_3); c – $\text{Ca}_3\text{Fe}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.84}(\text{OH})_{8.64}$)

During the subsequent water leaching step all soluble Na/K-tungstates were removed and the solid residue consisted of unreacted tungsten-containing scheelite and ferberite, a reaction product $\text{Ca}_3\text{Fe}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_{0.84}(\text{OH})_{8.64}$, as well as minor phases, such as quartz (SiO_2), calcite (CaCO_3) and fluoroapatite ($\text{Ca}_3\text{F}(\text{PO}_4)_3$). At 150 °C - 200 °C, substantially more unreacted scheelite remained in the residues of the samples fused with pure NaOH (Figure 1), highlighting the importance of the low-melting eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture as a key factor to

lower the fusion reaction temperature. Fusion at 500 °C and subsequent water leaching removed nearly all crystalline W-containing mineral phases. During the water leaching step almost no calcium was extracted into the pregnant leach solution (i.e., about 0.1-0.5 %). Thus, the formed Ca(OH)₂ during alkaline fusion dissolved in contact with water and re-precipitated in the leach residue as calcite (CaCO₃) and as a calcium-rich silicate hydroxide (Ca₃Fe₂(SiO₄)_{0.84}(OH)_{8.64}) also known as silicious hydro-garnet. The carbonate anions which formed CaCO₃ were likely supplied through adsorption of CO₂ from air during handling of the fused material. This material contains a considerable amount of hydroxides, such as Ca(OH)₂, NaOH and/or KOH, which are all known to act as solid sorbents of atmospheric CO₂ (eq. 6-8) (Mourad et al., 2022; Rincón et al., 2023). Upon dissolution in water of Na₂CO₃ and/or K₂CO₃, the carbonate anion can precipitate with Ca²⁺ cations as the poorly soluble CaCO₃ (eq. 9-11).

The tungsten extraction yield for material that was MW-fused in the eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture was similar for all tested fusion temperatures (Figure 2). However, when fused in NaOH at 150 °C the tungsten extraction yield in water was low (i.e., 5.2 ± 0.7%), but increased upon increasing the fusion temperature (Figure 2). Further, above a fusion temperature of 300 °C, the tungsten extraction yield was higher for the NaOH treated material than for the material fused in a NaOH:KOH mixture. However, the latter treatment gave a maximum tungsten

extraction yield of $81 \pm 5\%$ for the sample fused at $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and already $77 \pm 3\%$ at $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. SEM images and elemental mapping of tungsten in the original material showed large, sharp-edged scheelite particles present in the material. Whereas, after MW-assisted alkaline fusion in NaOH:KOH followed by water-leaching already for a fusion temperature of $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ the size of the scheelite particles was much reduced and the particle edges were more rounded (Figure S2). At $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ a small amount of tungsten containing particles were left, and after treatment at 300 ° and $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ no scheelite was observed anymore. Instead for the material fused in the presence of NaOH, the sharp-edged scheelite particles were still present after a $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ treatment and a significant amount of scheelite particles are still present for the $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ treated material, whereas for $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ fused material no tungsten was observed in the leaching residue (Figure S3).

Figure 2: W extraction yield of aqueous leached ($60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 2 h, L/S = 10) MW-assisted alkaline fused high-grade tungsten ore (DB-26) material at different fusion temperatures and in the

presence of either NaOH or an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture (30 min, sample:salt mass ratio of 1:1).

Alkaline MW-assisted fusion experiments on the intermediate-grade tungsten ore material (DB-91) showed that the elements tungsten, arsenic, sulphur and phosphorous, known to form soluble oxyanions in alkaline conditions, displayed an increase in leachability in water (60 °C, 2 h, L/S = 10) upon increasing fusion time in the case of using NaOH fusion alkali salt (Figure 3). Whereas, for fusion in the presence of an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture a similar increase in leachability was also observed for arsenic, sulphur and phosphorous, but not for tungsten. The leachability of other measured matrix elements (Al, Ca, Fe, Mg, Ti) remained low for all investigated fusion temperatures. Therefore, the ideal MW-assisted alkaline fusion reaction parameters for the intermediate-grade scheelite ore material (DB-91) are the use of an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture(1:1 (m/m)) in the temperature range of 150 °C – 200 °C as under these conditions the co-dissolution of arsenic and phosphorous remained low, and the fusion temperature was kept to a minimum value.

Figure 3: Aqueous leachability (60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 2 h, L/S = 10) of W, As, P, S, Al, Ca, Fe, Mg and Ti for MW-assisted alkaline fused intermediate-grade SAL ore (DB-91) as function of fusion temperature (30 min, salt:sample ratio = 1:1 (m/m)) for materials fused in NaOH (top) or NaOH:KOH = 1:1 (m/m) (bottom).

Interestingly, upon increasing the reaction temperature the formation of Na_2SiO_3 was observed in the fused materials as the presence of crystalline quartz and other silicate minerals decreased (Figure 4). It is well-known that quartz and silicates react in strong alkaline environments to form alkali silicates (Tchadjié et al., 2016). XRD diffractograms of the fused material and the leach residues (Figure 4) show that the leach residue of material fused at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an eutectic

salt mixture did not contain any crystalline scheelite phase. Whereas, scheelite was still present in the NaOH treated material at 150 °C. After water-leaching the recovered residues contained considerably less clinochlore and microcline mineral phases with respect to the original ore material (Figure 4). Furthermore, upon increasing the reaction temperature, the intensity of the remaining silicate mineral phases in the leach residues decreased, particularly for the NaOH fused material.

Figure 4: XRD analyses of DB-91 material MW-assisted fused at different temperatures for 30 min in the presences of NaOH (top left) or NaOH:KOH = 1:1 (m/m) (top right), both with a sample:salt mass ratio of 1:1. The diffractogram of the water-leaching residues (60 °C, 2 h, L/S = 10) of the fused samples are depicted below. (S – scheelite (CaWO_4); Q – quartz (SiO_2); A – albite ($\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$); M – muscovite ($\text{KAl}_2(\text{Si},\text{Al})_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$); m – microcline (KAlSi_3O_8); C – clinochlore ($(\text{Mg},\text{Fe},\text{Al})_6(\text{Si},\text{Al})_4\text{O}_{10}$); N – Na_2SiO_3 ; n – $\text{Na}_6\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$; P – pyrite (FeS_2))

The possibility to lower the alkali salt addition during fusion was further investigated. Therefore, alkaline fusion experiments at different sample:salt mass ratios of 1:1 (50 %), 3:1 (75 %) and 9:1 (90 %) were performed at 200 °C (20 min heating, 30 min dwell and 60 min cooling), followed by water leaching at 60 °C for 2 h at L/S = 10. Upon decreasing the salt to sample ratio, the leachability of W and other elements decreased for the intermediate-grade ore material (3.67 wt% W) (Figure S4 (left), SI). A similar observation was made for the DB-141 material which has a lower tungsten content of 1.0 wt% (Figure S5, SI). Therefore, the sample:salt ratio needs to be maintained at 1:1 (m/m) and the ratio appears to be independent of the tungsten content.

Two parameters were varied to optimise the MW-assisted fusion time, namely the ramp time and the dwell time. The ramp time refers to the time needed to heat the MW-furnace from room temperature to the set temperature, and the dwell time refers to the time for which the sample is kept at the set temperature. For all experiments a cooling time of 60 min was applied. Samples of the DB-91 material were MW-assisted fused at 200 °C in the presence of an eutectic mixture of NaOH:KOH = 1:1 (m/m) at a sample:salt ratio of 1:1 (m/m). Both the tested ramp and dwell times of the MW-assisted fusion step at 200 °C did not influence the subsequent water leachability of tungsten (Figure S4 (right), SI). Thus, a short MW-assisted fusion process of 10 min ramp and 10 min dwell can be applied to the DB-91 material.

The water leaching step reaction parameters temperature, such as time and L/S, were further optimised for the intermediate tungsten ore material (DB-91) that underwent MW-assisted alkaline fusion at 200 °C for 30 min (20 min ramp, 30 min dwell and 60 min cool) with a sample:salt ratio of 1:1 (m/m) and a salt mixture of NaOH:KOH = 1:1 (m/m). The tungsten leaching efficiency at 60 °C did not vary much by lowering the leaching time from 120 min to 30 min, whereas it did decrease slightly with decreasing reaction temperature for 120 min

leaching (Figure 5). For all tested leaching parameters, the leachability of the measured matrix elements Al, Ca, Fe, Mg and Ti was low. Thus, leaching could be performed at relatively short times (30 min), but preferably at higher leaching temperatures (i.e., 60 °C – 80 °C). At 60 °C the tungsten leaching efficiency was $94.7 \pm 0.3\%$.

Figure 5: Extraction yield of elements (W, S, As, P, Al, Ca, Fe, Mg and Ti) from MW-assisted alkaline fused DB-91 material as a function of water leaching ($L/S = 10$, 60 °C) time (right) and water leaching ($L/S = 10$, 120 min) temperature (left).

Still, it should be noted that already ca. 90% of tungsten could be water leached at lower temperature (i.e., 25 °C) in 30 min, which might be interesting from an industrial perspective. While the main matrix elements (Al, Ca, Fe) displayed limited dissolution ($<3\%$) during water leaching at 60 °C, significant co-extraction of phosphorous ($E_L = 45\%$), sulphur ($E_L = 80\%$) and arsenic ($E_L = 53\%$) occurred and could not be prevented.

Finally, the optimized process parameters for DB-91 were validated for the preconcentrated gravity tailings (DB-141). The pre-concentrated gravity tailings material (DB-141), in comparison to the intermediate SAL ore material (DB-91) contains lower amounts of W, S and As but higher concentrations of P, Al, Ca and Fe. Nevertheless, the mineral constituents of both materials are the same (Figure S1), with slight differences in the actual amounts of the different mineral phases present in both materials. Therefore, a similar reaction behaviour would be

expected. Thus, DB-141 underwent MW-fusion at 200 °C for 10 min heating and 10 min dwell in the presence of alkaline eutectic salt mixtures of NaOH:KOH (i.e., 1:1 (m/m)). A tungsten leaching efficiency of $95 \pm 3\%$ was obtained. Also, for this material, phosphorous ($54 \pm 13\%$), sulphur ($62 \pm 4\%$) and arsenic ($65 \pm 5\%$) extraction took place, whereas the extractions of the measured matrix elements were low (i.e., Al, Ca and Fe). Together with W, also P, S and As leached, which had all similar concentrations in the obtained leachate (i.e., in the range 418 – 560 mg/L), whereas the concentrations of the matrix elements (Al, Ca, Fe) were low (Table S2).

The gravity tailing material had the lowest tungsten-content (i.e., 1060 mg/kg) of all tested materials in this study. This material underwent MW-assisted alkane fusion at different temperatures in the presence of a sample:salt ratio (m/m) of 1:1, whereby the salt was either NaOH or a 1:1 (m/m) mixture of NaOH:KOH. In a subsequent water leaching step (L/S = 10, 60 °C, 120 min) the tungsten leachability was high for all studied fusion temperatures and salts (Figure 6). However, in the case of the eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture, the tungsten leaching efficiency for the 150 °C fused material was higher ($97 \pm 8\%$) than for the samples fused at the same temperature NaOH ($75 \pm 16\%$). Also in the eutectic NaOH:KOH salt mixture at 150 °C a minimal co-dissolution of the measured matrix elements (i.e., Al, Ca, Fe and Ti) was observed, whereas the extraction of phosphorous and sulphur remained $<60\%$.

Figure 6: Aqueous leachability ($L/S = 10$, 60 °C, 120 min) of W, P, S, Al, Ca, Fe and Ti for MW-assisted alkaline fused low-grade SAL gravity tailings (DB-52) as function of fusion temperature (20 min heating, 30 min dwell, 60 min cooling, salt:sample ratio = $1:1$ (m/m)) for materials fused in NaOH (top) or NaOH:KOH = $1:1$ (m/m) (bottom).

Alkaline microwave-assisted fusion of a columbite concentrate

MW-assisted fusion of the tantalum/niobium concentrate DB-139 sample was investigated at a chosen sample:salt ratio of $1:3$ (m/m) based on literature reporting the application of sample:salt ratios in the range of $1:2 - 1:5$ (m/m) (Table 1). Pure KOH, typically used in conventional alkaline fusion of tantalum/niobium ores (Table 1) and an equimolar NaOH:KOH

eutectic mixture were used as alkaline salts. The MW-fusion took place at four chosen temperatures (i.e., 200 °C, 300 °C, 400 °C and 500 °C) with a ramp time of 20 min, dwell time of 60 min and cooling time of 60 min. Next, the samples were water-leached at an L/S = 10 at 40 °C for 2 h. MW-assisted alkaline fusion of columbite/tantalite mineral phases take place according to the following reaction equations (eq. 12-13) wherein A = Na, K (Abdel Wahab et al., 2019; Shikika et al., 2021).

Upon analysing the elemental composition of the leach residues, the leaching efficiencies of tantalum and niobium increased upon increasing fusion temperature and were superior when the fusion took place in the presence of KOH (Figure 7, left). Whereas, the leaching efficiency of tantalum and niobium could not be determined by analysing their concentrations in the obtained lixivants for the experiments executed in the presence of an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture, as the obtained solution was instable and a precipitate formed.

Figure 7: Leaching efficiencies (water, 40 °C, 2 h, L/S = 10) of MW-assisted fused tantalum/niobium concentrate material DB-139 in the presence of KOH or an eutectic equimolar NaOH:KOH mixture. Top: Ta and Nb leaching efficiencies calculated based on EDXRF analysis of the leach residues (left) and ICP of the leachates (right). Bottom: leaching efficiencies of matrix elements for the material fused in the presence of KOH (left) or of an equimolar NaOH:KOH mixture (right).

The main matrix elements silicon and aluminium (Figure 7) also leached. Aluminium clearly showed a decreasing leachability as a function of increasing fusion temperature, whereas for silicon no clear trend as a function of fusion temperature could be observed. The leachability of both elements was higher when fusion in the presence of an equimolar NaOH:KOH mixture took place, with respect to pure KOH. Samples treated at 200 °C during fusion did not leach

tin, whereas the tin leachability increased for fusion temperatures of 300 °C and 400 °C. A further increase of fusion temperature to 500 °C decreased again the tin leachability. For most fusion temperatures manganese and iron did not leach in the water leaching step, whereas for samples fused at 500 °C the manganese leachability slightly increased.

Next the effect of MW-assisted alkaline fusion time was investigated. The sample:salt ratio was 1:3 (m/m) and both pure KOH and an equimolar NaOH:KOH mixture were tested. The MW-fusion took place at 400 °C with varying ramp times of 10 min or 20 min, and dwell times of 10 min, 30 min and 60 min. The cooling time was kept constant at 60 min. After the MW-assisted alkaline fusion, the samples were water-leached at an L/S = 10 at 40 °C for 2 h. For the KOH fused sample, the short ramp (10 min) and dwell (10 min) times gave the highest tantalum and niobium extraction efficiencies (Figure 8 top left).

Figure 8: Leaching efficiencies (water, 40 °C, 2 h, L/S = 10) of Ta and Nb, based on ICP analyses of the leachates (top) and EDXRF analyses of the leach residues (bottom), of the DB-

139 sample which underwent MW-assisted alkaline fusion at different ramp and dwell times at 400 °C in the presence of either KOH (left) or an equimolar NaOH:KOH mixture (right) with a sample:salt mass ratio of 1:3.

Again, a lower leaching efficiency could be observed when an equimolar mixture of NaOH:KOH was applied in the MW-assisted fusion step (Figure 8 right). Furthermore, when the leaching efficiencies were derived from ICP analyses of the obtained leachates a very low leachability was obtained due to precipitation of niobium and tantalum in the lixiviant, which was removed via a syringe filter prior to ICP analysis. Upon comparing the freshly obtained leachates, those of materials fused in the presence of the equimolar NaOH:KOH mixture were (slightly) lighter in colour with respect to those of the KOH fused materials. However, when the samples were left standing overnight, a precipitate formed for the NaOH:KOH fused material. Three precipitates were recovered and analysed whereby the solid was not washed prior to drying, therefore it contains traces of elements that were dissolved in the remaining liquid fraction in the filter cake. The tested precipitates contained mainly Na (11.9 – 12.6 wt%), K (7.6 – 12.7 wt%), Nb (15.2 – 16.3 wt%) and Ta (11.8 – 16.3 wt%) (Table S3), indicating that sodium and potassium niobate and tantalate salts precipitated from the alkaline leaching solution. Sodium niobate and tantalate are more stable than potassium niobate and tantalate, for which niobate and tantalate anions generally precipitate when a small amount of a sodium salt is added to a potassium niobate or niobate solution, respectively (Kennedy, 1961; Marks, 1929). Indeed, alkaline MW-assisted fusion with NaOH of a columbite concentrate also yielded a low tantalum and niobium extraction due to precipitation during aqueous leaching (Tanvar et al., 2023). The observation of precipitate formation in the filtrate solution does not exclude that partial tantalum and niobium precipitation already occurred in the reaction mixture prior to filtration.

Independently of the analysis method used, the best tantalum and niobium leaching efficiencies were observed when the concentrate material DB-139 was MW-fused at 400 °C in the presence of KOH for the shortest fusion times of 10 min ramp and 10 min dwell. The leaching efficiencies were $74 \pm 2\%$ Ta, $77 \pm 3\%$ Nb, when based on ICP of the lixiviant, and $85 \pm 1\%$ Ta, $85 \pm 2\%$ Nb when based on EDXRF of the leach residue.

Compared to the state of the art (Table 1) where a similar coltan ore material was treated by Shikika *et al.* (2021) (Shikika et al., 2021) than the material applied in this study, the obtained tantalum and niobium leaching efficiencies were similar, but a considerably lower fusion temperature (i.e., 400 °C vs. 500 °C) and time (i.e., 10 min vs. 60 min) were applied in this study with the assistance of MW-heating.

Conclusions

MW-assisted alkaline fusion was explored to extract tungsten (W) from scheelite (CaWO_4) containing ore materials with different grades (high to very low) and was also applied to a columbite concentrate material to investigate its applicability towards tantalum (Ta) and Niobium (Nb) recovery. For all tested ore grades scheelite was converted into soluble alkali tungstate salts [Na_2WO_4 , K_2WO_4 and/or $\text{K}_3\text{Na}(\text{WO}_4)_2$] and the fusion reaction temperature could be lowered to 150-200 °C by fusion with a low-melting eutectic alkali salt system consisting of an 1:1 (m/m) mixture of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and potassium hydroxide (KOH). Fusion is performed via MW-assisted heating instead of conventional heating to enable fast and volumetric heating, thereby lowering reaction times to 10 min – 30 min. After fusion, in a second step, the (cooled) MW-fused material was brought into contact with water to leach the soluble tungstate salt. For tungsten primary and secondary ore materials with tungsten concentrations of 52.6 wt%, 3.67 wt%, 1.05 wt% and 0.11 wt%, leaching efficiencies of 77%, 95%, 95% and 97%, respectively, could be achieved by fusion for short times (30 min) and at

low temperatures (150 – 200 °C) in the presence of NaOH:KOH (1:1 (m/m)) with a sample:salt ratio of 1:1 (m/m). Noteworthy, also P, S and As, which all form soluble oxyanions are extracted from the materials. These oxyanions could be competitive to the tungstate oxyanion in subsequent refining steps and need to be taken into account when studying such processing steps. Also, the harsh alkaline conditions transform quartz and other silicate minerals in reactive Na_2SiO_3 during the fusion process, in particular at high temperatures. Therefore, working at lower reaction temperatures can be advantageous to maintain matrix elements in their original mineral phase composition.

Extraction of niobium (Nb) and tantalum (Ta) from columbite-tantalite $[(\text{Fe},\text{Mn})(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_6]$ is important to process Nb and/or Ta resources, including low-grade ores or tailings, to access these critical raw materials. The solubilisation of both metals can be achieved through MW-assisted alkaline fusion as an alternative to acidic fluorine-based hydrometallurgical processes. MW-assisted heating allowed for a fast conversion (10 min at 400 °C) of the $(\text{Fe},\text{Mn})(\text{Nb},\text{Ta})_2\text{O}_6$ into alkali tantalate and niobate salts. Under optimal conditions, MW-assisted fusion of a columbite concentrate DB-139 with KOH (salt/sample = 3) at 400 °C for 10 min leaches ca. 74%-88% of tantalum and 77%-86% of niobium into water (L/S = 10) at 40 °C for 120 min, while the main matrix elements Mn and Fe displayed limited dissolution (<4%). Nevertheless, Sn, Si and Al leached considerably. Due to the low solubility of sodium tantalate and niobate salts, MW-assisted alkaline fusion in an eutectic NaOH:KOH mixture is not recommendable, as after aqueous leaching a fast precipitation of tantalates and niobates in the lixiviant occurred.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the TARANTULA project which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement

n°821159. This paper reflects only the author's views and neither Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

References

Abdel Wahab, G.M., Abdellah, W.M., Yousif, A.M., Mubark, A.E., Preparation of Pure Nb₂O₅ from Gabal El-Faliq Pegmatite, South Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Mining, Metallurgy & Exploration*, 2019, **39(2)**, 833-846.

Abo Atia, T., Spooren, J., Microwave assisted alkaline roasting-water leaching for the valorisation of goethite sludge from zinc refining process. *Hydrometallurgy*, 2020a, **191**, 105235.

Abo Atia, T., Spooren, J., Microwave assisted chloride leaching of zinc plant residues. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 2020b, **398**.

Abo Atia, T., Wouters, W., Monforte, G., Spooren, J., Microwave chloride leaching of valuable elements from spent automotive catalysts: Understanding the role of hydrogen peroxide. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 2021, **166**.

Baker, L.J., Parker, J.D., Daniel, S.R., Mechanism of bake hardening in ultralow carbon steel containing niobium and titanium additions. *Materials Science and Technology*, 2002, **18(5)**, 541-547.

Berhe, G.G., del Rosario, A.V., Abubeker, Y., Girma, W., Bogale, T., Sisay, C.M., Green extraction of Niobium and Tantalum from Kenticha Tantalite ore using 1-Ethyl-3-Methyl Imidazolium Chloride ionic liquid. *J Min Environ*, 2018, **9(4)**, 785-794.

Bohnet, M., *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*. 2003, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, Germany.

Cardonne, S.M., Kumar, P., Michaluk, C.A., Schwartz, H.D., Tantalum and Its Alloys. *Int J Refract Met H*, 1995, **13(4)**, 187-194.

Chen, W.S., Ho, H.J., Lin, K.Y., Hydrometallurgical Process for Tantalum Recovery from Epoxy-Coated Solid Electrolyte Tantalum Capacitors. *Materials (Basel)*, 2019, **12(8)**.

Choi, I.H., Moon, G., Lee, J.Y., Jyothi, R.K., Alkali fusion using sodium carbonate for extraction of vanadium and tungsten for the preparation of synthetic sodium titanate from spent SCR catalyst. *Sci Rep*, 2019, **9(1)**, 12316.

DG GROW - European Commission, 2023. Study on the Critical Raw Materials for the EU 2023.

El-Hussaini, O.M., Mahdy, M.A., Sulfuric acid leaching of Kab Amiri niobium–tantalum bearing minerals, Central Eastern Desert, Egypt. *Hydrometallurgy*, 2002, **64(3)**, 219-229.

Finnemore, D.K., Stromberg, T.F., Swenson, C.A., Superconducting Properties of High-Purity Niobium. *Physical Review*, 1966, **149(1)**, 231-243.

Foster, R.P., Solubility of Scheelite in Hydrothermal Chloride Solutions. *Chemical Geology*, 1977, **20(1)**, 27-43.

Habinshuti, J.B., Munganyinka, J.P., Himanshu, T., Adetunji, A.R., Mishra, B., Mukiza, J., Ofori-Sarpong, G., Onwualu, A.P., Fluoride-free, simple, and environmentally friendly extraction of mixed oxides of niobium and tantalum from the Nigerian and Rwandan columbite-tantalite concentrates. *Minerals Engineering*, 2023, **201**.

Irabien, A., Viguri, J.R., Ortiz, I., Thermal dehydration of calcium hydroxide. 1. Kinetic model and parameters. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 1990, **29(8)**, 1599-1606.

Kennedy, J.H., Sodium-potassium niobates and tantalates. *Journal of Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry*, 1961, **20(1-2)**, 53-57.

Krismer, B., Hoppe, A., 1984. Process for recovering niobium and/or tantalum compounds from such ores further containing complexes of uranium, thorium, tinanium and/ore rare earth metals. Starck Bertin, Hermann C., United States of America.

Lassner, E., From Tungsten Concentrates and Scrap to Highly Pure Ammonium Paratungstate (Apt). *Int J Refract Met H*, 1995, **13(1-3)**, 35-44.

Majima, H., Awakura, Y., Mashima, M., Hirato, T., Dissolution of Columbite and Tantalite in Acidic Fluoride Media. *Metall Trans B*, 1988, **19(3)**, 355-363.

Marks, S., *Volume VI. Part III. Vanadium, niobium and tantalum*. 1929, Charles Griffin & Company Limited, London.

Mourad, A.A.H., Mohammad, A.F., Al-Marzouqi, A.H., Altarawneh, M., Al-Marzouqi, M.H., El-Naas, M.H., Carbon dioxide capture through reaction with potassium hydroxide and reject brine: A kinetics study. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 2022, **120**.

Peng, Z., Hwang, J.-Y., Microwave-assisted metallurgy. *International Materials Reviews*, 2014, **60(1)**, 30-63.

Pickles, C.A., Microwaves in extractive metallurgy: Part 1 – Review of fundamentals. *Minerals Engineering*, 2009a, **22(13)**, 1102-1111.

Pickles, C.A., Microwaves in extractive metallurgy: Part 2 – A review of applications. *Minerals Engineering*, 2009b, **22(13)**, 1112-1118.

Pinto, I.S.S., Soares, H.M.V.M., Microwave-assisted selective leaching of nickel from spent hydrodesulphurization catalyst: A comparative study between sulphuric and organic acids. *Hydrometallurgy*, 2013, **140**, 20-27.

Rincón, L., Ruiz, C., Contreras, R.R., Almarza, J., Study of the NaOH(s)–CO₂(g) reaction creating value for industry: green natrite production, energy, and its potential in different sustainable scenarios. *Environmental Science: Advances*, 2023, **2(7)**, 957-966.

Sanchez-Segado, S., Monti, T., Katrib, J., Kingman, S., Dodds, C., Jha, A., Towards sustainable processing of columbite group minerals: elucidating the relation between dielectric properties and physico-chemical transformations in the mineral phase. *Sci Rep*, 2017, **7(1)**, 18016.

Shikika, A., Muvundja, F., Mugumaoderha, M.C., Gaydardzhiev, S., Extraction of Nb and Ta from a coltan ore from South Kivu in the DRC by alkaline roasting – thermodynamic and kinetic aspects. *Minerals Engineering*, 2021, **163**.

Spooren, J., Abo Atia, T., Combined microwave assisted roasting and leaching to recover platinum group metals from spent automotive catalysts. *Minerals Engineering*, 2020, **146**.

Spooren, J., Binnemans, K., Björkmalm, J., Breemersch, K., Dams, Y., Folens, K., González-Moya, M., Horckmans, L., Komnitsas, K., Kurylak, W., Lopez, M., Mäkinen, J., Onisei, S., Oorts, K., Peys, A., Pietek, G., Pontikes, Y., Snellings, R., Tripiana, M., Varia, J., Willquist, K., Yurramendi, L., Kinnunen, P., Near-zero-waste processing of low-grade, complex primary ores and secondary raw materials in Europe: technology development trends. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 2020, **160**, 104919.

Srinivas, K., Sreenivas, T., Natarajan, R., Padmanabhan, N.P.H., Studies on the recovery of tungsten from a composite wolframite-scheelite concentrate. *Hydrometallurgy*, 2000, **58(1)**, 43-50.

Tanvar, H., Mishra, B., Fluoride-Free Processing of Columbite Concentrate for Selective Recovery of Niobium and Tantalum Oxides. *Mining, Metallurgy & Exploration*, 2024, **41(2)**, 515-523.

Tanvar, H., Sinha, M.K., Habinshuti, J.B., Mishra, B., Extraction of Niobium and Tantalum Oxides From Columbite Concentrate Using Microwave Processing and Solvent Extraction. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B*, 2023, **54(2)**, 621-634.

Tchadjié, L.N., Djobo, J.N.Y., Ranjbar, N., Tchakouté, H.K., Kenne, B.B.D., Elimbi, A., Njopwouo, D., Potential of using granite waste as raw material for geopolymer synthesis. *Ceramics International*, 2016, **42(2)**, 3046-3055.

Wang, X., Zheng, S., Xu, H., Zhang, Y., Leaching of niobium and tantalum from a low-grade ore using a KOH roast–water leach system. *Hydrometallurgy*, 2009, **98(3-4)**, 219-223.

Wen, T., Zhao, Y., Xiao, Q., Ma, Q., Kang, S., Li, H., Song, S., Effect of microwave-assisted heating on chalcopyrite leaching of kinetics, interface temperature and surface energy. *Results in Physics*, 2017, **7**, 2594-2600.